

An 18 year old phenotypically male raised as female. A case report

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Abstract

Introduction

Hermaphroditism is an anatomical pathological diagnosis based on the findings of testicular and ovarian tissues in the same subject, in the same gonad, or in separate gonads. It is a sex ambiguity, and the most common karyotype is 46XX. Mosaics and chimeras are found in only 2%. We present a case report of phenotypically male raised as female.

Key words: Eighteen-year-old, phenotypically male, raised as female, hermaphroditism.

Case report

An 18 year old phenotypically male who was raised as a female was referred to our gynaecological clinic for investigation of sex ambiguity. He was the first child of the parents with uneventful pregnancy and delivery. The mother is late, but he was assessed to have had sex ambiguity at birth and he was taken to a hospital for a minor surgery after birth. He was considered as female right from then and raised as such.

He finished primary school, but could not further his education due to lack of sponsorship. He is usually locked up in the room, but allowed occasional interaction with other girls. He is always seen in hijab just to conceal the beard from being seen by other female friends.

Physical examination revealed a short stature male like person with beard which was deliberately shaved from time to time to enabled him look like female. No breast development and no history of menarche. There were no phallus and testes. The ambiguous external genitalia showed a prominent midline ridge held down by the skin from the pubis to the perineum. The ridge is surrounded on both sides with skin rugae that looks like empty scrotal sacs. At the tip of the ridge which tapered towards the perineum is found the external urethral meatus and a blind ended dimple like vagina orifice as seen in Figure 1. There were male patterns of hair distributions in the axilla, chest, chin and pubic areas. His voice was deep as well. There was no palpable mass within the inguinal area bilaterally.

He was to do an abdomino - pelvic ultrasound scan, hormonal profile and karyotype but lost to follow up.

Figure 1: Clinical photograph of the ambiguous external genitalia.

Discussions

Ambiguous genitalia or atypical genitalia, is a rare disorder of sexual development where a newborn external genitalia do not appear typically male or female, affecting roughly 1 in 2,000 to 4500 births [1]. It results from hormonal or chromosomal irregularities in utero, often involving conditions like Congenital Adrenal Hyperplasia (CAH) or androgen insensitivity [2]. It is considered a medical emergency requiring multidisciplinary care to determine sex assignment.

The most common cause is Congenital Adrenal Hyperplasia (CAH), which produces excess androgens with female fetus (46xx). Other causes include sex chromosome abnormalities like Turner syndrome, or Klinefelter syndrome, androgen insensitivity syndrome or 5-alpha-reductase deficiency [3].

Diagnosis involves rapid testing including chromosomal analysis (karyotyping) to determine genetic sex, blood tests for hormone levels and imaging (ultrasound) to identify internal structures such as testes, uterus and ovaries. The index patient presented late and was lost to follow up hence the diagnosis was not established beyond physical features.

References

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Management requires a multidisciplinary team involving paediatrics at birth, endocrinologists, surgeons, geneticist, and psychologists. Treatment is tailored to the specific cause and may involve hormonal therapy and or surgery; sometimes the individual can participate in decision making. The index client was 18 years and has been raised as female but not comfortable with the raised sex. The diagnosis was not established beyond physical characteristics as he was lost to follow up.

In conclusion, ambiguous genitalia is a worrisome condition both to parents and individual involved specially to those diagnosed at advanced age and raised in particular sex without stabilised diagnosis. It causes a lot of psychological trauma on how such individuals are raised. Early diagnosis and multidisciplinary approach will go a long way to help such clients and their parents.

No conflict of interest

Consent obtained for the use of photograph